

The Pedagogical Necessity Of Improving The Professional Skills Of Students Based On The Study Of The History Of Uzbek Musical Instruments

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Annotation: This article scientifically and theoretically substantiates the pedagogical necessity of improving the professional skills of future music specialists based on the systematic study of the history of Uzbek musical instruments. The study analyzes the stages of historical formation of Uzbek national musical instruments, performing traditions, and the role of the teacher-student school in the educational process. It also highlights the possibilities of developing performing skills, national musical thinking, professional motivation, and creative approach in students by integrating historical and cultural heritage into the educational process. The article reveals the pedagogical significance of teaching the history of Uzbek instrumental performance in higher educational institutions and puts forward methodological recommendations for combining it with practical training.

Keywords: Uzbek instrumental performance, professional qualifications, music education, pedagogical necessity, performing traditions, teacher-student school, historical approach, creative competence.

Introduction

In today's conditions of globalization and cultural integration, the issue of preserving the national art and musical heritage and combining it with the modern education system is of particular pedagogical importance. In particular, in the process of forming the professional qualifications of future specialists in the music education system, one of the urgent tasks is to provide education based on national values, historical traditions and performing schools. From this point of view, a deep and systematic study of the history of Uzbek musical performance is one of the important factors in preparing students as professionally mature, national musical thinkers, and creative thinkers.

Uzbek musical performance has a centuries-old history, which embodies the spiritual world, aesthetic views, historical memory, and cultural thinking of the people. The formation and development of national musical instruments such as tanbur, dutar, rubab, gijjak, nay, chang is important not only from the point of view of musical art, but also from the point of view of pedagogical experience. After all, the performing traditions, methodological schools, and the teacher-student system formed on the basis of these instruments have created an effective model of music education.

Currently, although attention to performance technique has increased among students studying music in higher educational institutions, in many cases the historical

and cultural foundations, the origin of performance schools, and the characteristics of national style are not sufficiently mastered. This situation leads to the inability of students to fully demonstrate performance in their professional activities, which is focused only on technical performance, but is rich in content and has a national spirit. Therefore, there is a need to include the history of Uzbek instrumental performance in the educational process on a pedagogical basis and to inextricably link it with practical exercises.

From a pedagogical point of view, studying the history of Uzbek instrumental performance serves to comprehensively form professional knowledge, skills, and competencies in students. In particular, through historical knowledge, students develop a sense of respect and responsibility for national music, and the ability to consciously use traditional stylistic features in the performance process is developed. This process has a positive impact on the formation of the student not only as a performer, but also as a teacher and a cultural propagandist. Also, studying the history of Uzbek instrumental performance encourages students to think independently, take an analytical approach, and engage in creative research. Through a comparative analysis of performance styles from different historical periods and the study of the performance schools of famous musicians, students have the opportunity to form their own performance style. This is one of the important pedagogical conditions for improving their professional qualifications.

Improving the professional skills of students based on the study of the history of Uzbek instrumental performance is a theoretical and practical important pedagogical necessity in today's music education system. Research conducted in this area serves to enrich the content of national music education, improve the quality of education, and prepare competitive, national and universal values-embodied specialists.

Discussion:

When discussing the issue of improving the professional skills of students based on the study of the history of Uzbek instrumental performance, it is necessary, first of all, to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the impact of this process on the content of education and pedagogical results. Practical experience shows that historical knowledge in music education is not limited to providing information, but also serves as an important factor in the formation of the student's performing thinking, aesthetic taste, and professional identity.

Firstly, a systematic study of the history of Uzbek instrumental performance strengthens the conscious approach of students to their performing activities. In the process of getting acquainted with historical periods, performing schools and the work of famous musicians, students begin to understand the capabilities of the instrument more deeply. As a result, performance is viewed not only as a technical exercise, but also as a complex creative process expressing an artistic image. This situation serves

to raise professional qualifications to a qualitatively new level.

Secondly, in the issue under discussion, the pedagogical significance of the teacher-student tradition deserves special attention. In the history of Uzbek instrumental performance, the direct transmission of knowledge and experience from generation to generation has been the main educational model. In the modern higher education system, reinterpreting this tradition on a scientific and methodological basis, that is, applying the principles of an individual approach, teaching by example and creative communication to the teaching process, provides high efficiency in improving the professional qualifications of students. This confirms the relevance of using national experience in pedagogical activities.

Thirdly, the historical approach is an important factor in the formation of national musical thinking in students. If the national style, melodic features, rhythmic and formal peculiarities are not sufficiently understood in the performance process, generality and simplicity will prevail in the performance. Studying the history of Uzbek instrumental performance allows students to interpret traditional performance methods in accordance with modern requirements. This process develops professional flexibility and a creative approach.

Fourthly, it should be noted in the discussion that it is difficult to achieve high results without integrating historical knowledge with practical exercises. If historical materials are presented only in the form of lectures, they will not become stable professional skills in the student's mind. On the contrary, if each historical topic is linked to practical performance, repertoire selection, methodological analysis and stage culture, the professional competence of students will be further strengthened. This indicates that the combination of theory and practice in music education is a pedagogical necessity.

Fifth, studying the history of Uzbek musical performance is also an important factor in increasing students' professional motivation. The life and creative path of national musicians, their devotion to art and skill educate students in the spirit of love for the profession. This creates the basis for them to responsibly approach their activities as performers, teachers or researchers in the future.

The results of the discussion also show that the educational process based on the history of Uzbek instrumental performance adapts students not only to the national framework, but also to universal musical values. Based on comparative analysis, students have the opportunity to compare with the instrumental performance of other nations, to increase the breadth of musical thinking. This serves to form the intercultural competence required in modern education. Improving the professional skills of students based on the study of the history of Uzbek instrumental performance is a pedagogically sound, theoretically and practically effective direction. This approach allows enriching the content of music education, increasing the quality and

effectiveness of education, and preparing qualified specialists in harmony with national and modern requirements.

Literature analysis:

The issue of studying the history of Uzbek instrumental performance and improving the professional skills of students on its basis is being formed as a separate direction in musicology and pedagogical sciences. In the scientific substantiation of this problem, national and foreign studies, historical sources, pedagogical concepts and methodological developments serve as an important theoretical foundation.

First of all, an analysis of scientific literature on the history of Uzbek musical performance shows that this area is studied mainly from the point of view of musicology. The works of such scientists as V. Uspensky, Yu. Rajabiy, I. Akbarov, F. Karomatov, O. Matyokubov provide a detailed account of the origin, performing traditions, connection with the art of maqom, and stages of historical development of Uzbek national musical instruments. In these studies, musical performance is interpreted as an expression of the cultural memory and artistic thinking of the people. However, in most of these works, the historical-materialistic approach prevails, and the issue of their direct application to the pedagogical process is not sufficiently revealed.

In the literature on the methodology of music education, the influence of the historical approach on the effectiveness of education is emphasized. In studies conducted by Russian and foreign scholars (D. Kabalevsky, N. Vetlugina, etc.), historical-contextual analysis of a musical work is shown as an important factor in understanding and high-quality performance. These views scientifically substantiate the possibility of developing students' performance thinking by studying the history of Uzbek instrumental performance.

In local pedagogical research conducted in recent years, the issues of integrating national musical heritage into the educational process are gaining increasing attention. These studies emphasize that the use of national music samples increases patriotism, aesthetic taste, and professional motivation in students. However, most of these studies are focused on general music education, and the issue of studying the history of Uzbek musical performance in an inextricable link with improving students' professional skills has not been sufficiently explored.

The results of the analysis show that although the musicological aspects of the history of Uzbek instrumental performance have been sufficiently studied in the existing literature, the issue of its use in the pedagogical system as a means of improving professional training in higher education has not been comprehensively studied. It is this fact that determines the relevance of this study and creates a methodological basis for drawing new scientific conclusions. Therefore, in this article, integrating the achievements of musicology and pedagogical sciences, the aim is to scientifically illuminate the pedagogical possibilities of improving students'

professional skills based on the study of the history of Uzbek instrumental performance, aiming to fill the gap in the existing literature.

Conclusion.

The analysis conducted shows that improving students' professional skills based on the study of the history of Uzbek instrumental performance is an important pedagogical necessity for today's music education system. National instrumental performance has a rich historical and cultural experience formed over the centuries, and its scientific introduction into the educational process serves to ensure the professional development of future specialists. Also, the educational process, organized based on the history of Uzbek instrumental performance, allows combining the traditions of the teacher-student relationship with modern pedagogical approaches. This increases the effectiveness of teaching principles through an individual approach, creative dialogue and practical examples. As a result, students are formed not only as performers, but also as future music teachers and cultural propagators, possessing professional responsibility and creative potential. In conclusion, it is worth noting that the integration of the history of Uzbek instrumental performance into the educational process serves to enrich the content of music education, improve the quality and effectiveness of education. This approach is manifested as an important pedagogical factor in the development of national musical thinking, professional motivation and creative competencies in students.

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